
Journal of Social Science and Human Research Studies

Volume: 02 Issue: 06 June-2026

Research on Criteria for Evaluating the Effectiveness of Learning 5-A-Side Football for Students University of Finance - Marketing, Vietnam

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Published Date: June 09, 2026

Article DOI: 10.65150/EP-jsshhs/V2E6/2026-13

ABSTRACT: In the context of reforming physical education towards improving the quality and effectiveness of training, building a system of criteria for evaluating the learning effectiveness of 5-a-side football is of significant importance to teaching and learning at higher education institutions. This study aims to identify appropriate evaluation criteria, ensuring scientific validity, reliability, and practical applicability, contributing to improving the quality of teaching 5-a-side football to students at the University of Finance - Marketing, Vietnam (UFM). The study utilizes research methods such as document synthesis and analysis, interviews, and statistical mathematics to effectively address the research objectives. Research subjects: 28 experienced administrators, professionals, and lecturers in the field of Physical Education and Sports, and 187 students taking the 5-a-side football elective course (73 male, 114 female) at UFM. The sample was selected using a random and convenience sampling method. The research results identified eight criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of learning 5-a-side football for students at the University of Finance - Marketing, Vietnam, including: teaching staff, facilities for teaching and learning, curriculum content, extracurricular sports activities, students' need for sports training, students' interest in learning 5-a-side football, students' physical fitness level, and academic results.

KEYWORDS: Evaluation criteria, learning effectiveness, 5-a-side football, students, University of Finance - Marketing, Vietnam.

1. INTRODUCTION

Physical education (PE) in higher education is an important compulsory course in the training program, contributing to physical development, improving health, and fostering qualities, social skills, and professional competence among students [1], [2]. In the trend of educational innovation according to the competency-based approach and output standards, PE not only aims at the goal of developing physical fitness but also focuses on evaluating learning effectiveness through motor skills, ability to apply skills, attitude, and behavior of learners [3]. According to modern assessment perspectives, learning outcomes should be considered comprehensively based on output standards and performance competencies instead of just on achievements or scores (Shavelson, 2008; Sadler, 2009) [4], [5]. Current learning assessment models in higher education all emphasize measuring learners' achievement of practical competencies through a system of specific criteria and assessment standards.

In university-level physical education courses, 5-a-side football (Futsal) is a popular choice of sport due to its attractiveness, high competitiveness, and suitability to the school's facilities [6]. Compared to traditional football, Futsal is played on smaller pitches with fewer players, shorter ball handling time, high intensity, and requires players to constantly perform technical and tactical actions in a limited space. Players must have a high level of physical fitness, technical skills, and tactical awareness [7]. Futsal places a greater emphasis on skill, using a smaller and lighter ball. This is a good tool to help develop individual technique (Manescu, 2016; Naser et al., 2017) [8], [9]. This appeal stems from the fact that the sport emphasizes competitiveness and adaptability to various skill levels, making it accessible and suitable for a wide range of participants [7], [10].

According to the World Football Federation (FIFA), Futsal is an effective means to develop individual technique, tactical thinking, and situational handling ability for learners, and is considered an important foundation in modern sports education (FIFA, 2021) [11]. International studies also confirm that the dynamic nature of Futsal requires players to combine technique, physical fitness, tactical awareness, and psychosocial skills in both competition and learning. Therefore, the effectiveness of learning 5-a-side football needs to be assessed across multiple components instead of relying solely on individual technical tests.

For 5-a-side football, student learning effectiveness needs to be approached from a multi-component perspective, including: (1) professional knowledge and rules of the game; (2) ability to perform basic techniques such as dribbling, passing, receiving and shooting; (3) ability to apply tactics and make decisions; (4) professional physical fitness level; and (5) attitude, cooperative spirit and learning awareness. This view is consistent with the research of Nugroho and Tomoliyus (2019) [12], when building a Futsal performance evaluation tool based on indicators including skills, decision-making ability, team support and tactical reorganization; the results show that these criteria have high value and relatively fully reflect the performance of learners.

In recent years, research on Futsal learning assessment worldwide has made significant progress. The study by Nusri, A., et. Al. (2025) developed the Futsal Basic Skill Test Series (FBSTS) [6] for university students with an assessment system including tests of passing, dribbling, receiving, shooting, and handling real-life situations. The results show that the toolkit is highly reliable and valuable, and reflects the technical ability of learners well under conditions similar to actual competition. Similarly, Pelana et al. (2020) [13], when studying the Futsal training model and testing system for Indonesian university students, confirmed that building an assessment system based on practical skills significantly improves the learning efficiency and competition ability of students. Several studies have been conducted on the design of measurement tools that can be used to assess the level of mastery of techniques in football [14]. This development has made significant progress through numerous studies aimed at improving the validity and reliability of skill assessment. The development of a tool for measuring ball passing technique has been carried out and can be applied without the use of a support wall [15]. However, this tool still lacks clear guidelines in the implementation process, as well as specific criteria related to the age group and/or ability level of the subjects being assessed.

In addition, many recent studies have expanded the scope of Futsal assessment towards the development of comprehensive competencies. Mulloh et al. (2025) [16] argue that Futsal learning activities not only improve motor skills but also contribute to the development of life skills, communication skills, cooperation, and self-management of learners. This shows that the effectiveness of learning 5-a-side football needs to be viewed in an integrated way between the professional and social competencies of students.

In Vietnam, research on evaluating the learning outcomes of football in Physical Education has been of interest for many years, such as: Hieu, H. H (2024) identified 04 technical evaluation criteria and built technical evaluation standards for students studying Physical Education 3 subjects Football at Ho Chi Minh City University of Banking [17]; Manh, T. N. V. (2023) built theoretical and practical evaluation criteria in learning football for students [18] and Dung, T. P. D. (2022) identified 06 measures to improve the effectiveness of learning football in class hours for female students of Hanoi National University [19].

However, most current domestic studies mainly focus on physical education students or athletes, emphasizing the assessment of technical skills and professional physical fitness; meanwhile, research on criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of learning 5-a-side football for non-specialized students is relatively limited. In particular, there are not many studies that develop a comprehensive system of criteria that simultaneously reflect knowledge, skills, physical fitness, tactics, and learning attitudes oriented towards competency development.

At the University of Finance - Marketing, 5-a-side football is a Physical Education course chosen by a high percentage of students due to its attractiveness and suitability for the available playing fields. However, teaching practice shows that current learning outcomes are mainly assessed based on attendance, individual technical tests, and instructor comments; a comprehensive system of evaluation criteria that fully reflects student learning effectiveness has not yet been established. This leads to limitations in defining learning outcomes, adjusting teaching content, and improving training quality.

In the context of reforming physical education towards a competency-based approach and learning outcomes, there is a need to develop a scientifically-based system of criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of learning in 5-a-side football, suitable to the characteristics of the subject and the practical conditions of the school. This system of criteria will not only contribute to improving the quality of testing and evaluation but also serve as a basis for adjusting the curriculum, innovating teaching methods, and enhancing learning effectiveness for students.

Based on the above theoretical and practical foundations, conducting the research project: " Research on criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of learning 5-a-side football for students" is necessary and has urgent scientific and practical significance in the current period.

2. METHODOLOGY

Research Methods:

Document Analysis and Synthesis Method

This method helps researchers collect, analyze, and synthesize source materials by reading and taking notes on documents related to the criteria for evaluating learning outcomes in 5-a-side football. This method is used in most scientific research projects. It helps researchers gain more information about the theoretical basis, build scientific hypotheses, determine research objectives, and verify results during the research process.

Interview method

This research method was used to construct questionnaires and conduct surveys to collect indirect information based on the survey questionnaires. The survey questionnaires were developed based on references to documents and research works related to the research content of the thesis, focusing on the issue of physical education for students and evaluating the active participation of students in learning the physical education course.

The reliability of the survey questionnaires was tested in the following three steps:

- Step 1: Research relevant theories and draft an initial preliminary questionnaire.
- Step 2: Design a questionnaire to collect information related to the evaluation criteria.
- Step 3: Test the reliability of the questionnaire using Cronbach's Alpha.

After completing the validation and reliability tests of the survey questionnaire, the survey scale was finalized. The survey was then conducted using the questionnaires on UFM students.

Mathematical statistical methods

This method is used in the analysis and processing of data collected during the research on the topic. During processing, the data in the topic were entered and processed based on Excel software and SPSS data analysis for Windows version 20.0 [20].

Research Subjects

- + Survey on the selection of criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of 5-a-side football learning outcomes: 15 experienced managers, professionals, and lecturers in the field of Physical Education and Sports were selected using a judgmental and convenience sampling method.
- + A reliability test of the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of 5-a-side football learning outcomes was conducted using a convenient and random sampling method.
- + 187 students (73 male, 114 female) taking the 5-a-side football elective course at UFM were sampled using a convenience and random sampling method.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To select criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of 5-a-side football learning at the University of Finance - Marketing (UFM), this study designed an interview questionnaire and sent it to relevant faculty and lecturers involved in teaching physical education and 5-a-side football to gather feedback. The aim was to identify and select objective and consistent criteria for evaluating the teaching and learning of 5-a-side football at UFM. The study followed these steps:

- Step 1: Conduct theoretical research related to the criteria for evaluating physical education in universities and colleges in Ho Chi Minh City.
- Step 2: Design a questionnaire to collect information related to the criteria for evaluating physical education at UFM.
- Step 3: Design an interview questionnaire, identify the criteria, and confirm the reliability of the criteria for evaluating physical education at UFM.

3.1. The theoretical research results are related to the criteria for evaluating the teaching and learning of 5-a-side football at UFM.

Through documents, research works related to the research problem of the topic by authors such as: Hoang Ha (2016) [21]; Tran Duy Nam (2016) [22]; Nguyen Hung Anh (2013) [23]; Shavelson, R. J. (2008) [4], Sadler, D. R. (2009) [5], Nusri, A., et. al (2025) [6], C. O. Manescu (2016) [7], A. Goldasis (2016) [10], Nugroho, M. D., & Tomoliyus, T. (2019) [12], Pelana, R., et. al (2020) [13], M. Reis, J. et. al (2019) [14], R. I. Doewes, et. al (2022) [15], Mulloh, F., et. al (2025) [16], Hieu, H. H (2024) [17], Manh, T. N. V. (2023) [18], Dung, T. P. D. (2022) [19].... Based on previous research, this study analyzed and selected criteria used by many authors related to evaluating the current state of physical education and the learning of 5-a-side football at UFM, which are considered suitable for the school's current conditions, as summarized in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Selection of criteria for evaluating the current state of teaching and learning 5-a-side football at UFM

	Evaluation criteria	Number of research works used	Frequency (%)
1	Teaching staff requirements	18/18	100.00
2	Facilities and equipment for teaching and learning.	18/18	100.00
3	Content and curriculum	15/18	83.33
4	Extracurricular sports activities	10/18	55.55
5	The need for sports training among students.	17/18	94.44
6	Students' interest in learning 5-a-side football.	14/18	77.77
7	Students' physical fitness level	18/18	100.00
8	Academic results	18/18	100.00

Based on the results in Table 3.1, the study selected 8 criteria for evaluating the current state of teaching and learning 5-a-side football. The frequency of use of these criteria in the research works ranged from 14 to 18 out of 18, accounting for 55.55% to 100% of the 18 research works analyzed.

The most commonly used criteria in the aforementioned research works are: the qualifications of the teaching staff; the physical facilities for teaching and learning; the content and curriculum; extracurricular sports activities; students' need for sports training; students' interest in learning physical education; students' physical fitness level; and academic results.

3.2. The results of the research collected relate to the criteria for evaluating the teaching and learning of 5-a-side football at UFM.

To affirm the independence of the criteria for evaluating the current state of physical education at the University of Finance - Marketing, the study sent questionnaires to experts, managers, and lecturers with many years of experience in physical education at universities and colleges in Ho Chi Minh City.

Fifteen questionnaires were sent out and all fifteen were returned, representing a 100% response rate. Criteria with a selection rate of 80% or higher were used for evaluation. The combined results of the 15 opinions from experts, lecturers, and managers suggesting the use of criteria to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching and learning 5-a-side football at UFM are presented in Table 3.2, showing:

Table 3.2: Criteria for evaluating the current state of teaching and learning football at UFM (n = 15)

	Evaluation criteria	Person (Suggestion)	Ratio (%)
1	Teaching staff requirements	15/15	100.00
2	Facilities and equipment for teaching and learning.	15/15	100.00
3	Content and curriculum	15/15	100.00
4	Extracurricular sports activities	14/15	93.33
5	The need for sports training among students.	13/15	86.66
6	Students' interest in learning 5-a-side football.	14/15	93.33
7	Students' physical fitness level	15/15	100.00
8	Academic results	12/15	80.00

The summary of feedback from experts, managers, and relevant lecturers, as shown in Table 3.2, reveals that 7 criteria overlap with the 7 criteria analyzed and selected in Table 3.1, accounting for 86.66% - 100%. Additionally, 12 comments added the criterion "Assessment of student learning outcomes," representing 80%. Thus, the results of theoretical analysis and information gathering show that, in order to assess the current state of teaching and learning 5-a-side football at UFM, it is necessary to use all 8 criteria as presented in Table 3.2.

3.3. Testing the reliability of criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of 5-a-side football learning at UFM.

To ensure the reliability of the evaluation criteria, the study conducted theoretical analysis and data collection, designed an interview questionnaire, and sent it to 28 people (lecturers, experts, and physical education administrators) to determine and simultaneously test the reliability of the criteria. The results are presented in Table 3.3 as follows:

Table 3.3: Comparison of the selection levels of criteria for evaluating the teaching and learning of 5-a-side football at UFM.

Encryption	Criteria	Measurement level	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Q1	Teaching requirements staff	Normal	4	14.3	14.3	14.3
		Necessary	8	28.6	28.6	42.9
		Very necessary	16	57.1	57.1	100.0
		Total	28	100.0	100.0	
Q2	Facilities and equipment necessary for teaching and learning.	Normal	2	7.1	7.1	7.1
		Necessary	13	46.4	46.4	53.6
		Very necessary	13	46.4	46.4	100.0
		Total	28	100.0	100.0	
Q3	Content and curriculum	Normal	14	50.0	50.0	50.0
		Very necessary	14	50.0	50.0	100.0
		Total	28	100.0	100.0	
Q4		Normal	18	64.3	64.3	64.3

	Extracurricular sports activities	Very necessary	10	35.7	35.7	100.0
		Total	28	100.0	100.0	
Q5	The need for sports training among students.	Normal	4	14.3	14.3	14.3
		Necessary	13	46.4	46.4	60.7
		Very necessary	11	39.3	39.3	100.0
		Total	28	100.0	100.0	
Q6	Students' interest in learning 5-a-side football.	Necessary	12	42.9	42.9	42.9
		Very necessary	16	57.1	57.1	100.0
		Total	28	100.0	100.0	
Q7	Students' physical fitness level	Necessary	12	42.9	42.9	42.9
		Very necessary	16	57.1	57.1	100.0
		Total	28	100.0	100.0	
Q8	Academic results	Normal	7	25.0	25.0	25.0
		Necessary	11	39.3	39.3	64.3
		Very necessary	10	35.7	35.7	100.0
		Total	28	100.0	100.0	

The results in Table 3.3 show that the criterion "Teaching staff requirements" (Q1) was selected as normal by 4 people, accounting for 14.3%; as necessary by 8 people, accounting for 28.6%; and as very necessary by 16 people, accounting for 57.1%. The criterion "Facilities and equipment necessary for teaching and learning" (Q2) was selected by 2 people at the normal level, accounting for 7.1%; at the necessary level, it was selected by 13 people, accounting for 46.4%; and at the very necessary level, it was selected by 13 people, accounting for 46.4%. The criterion "Content and curriculum" (Q3) was selected as necessary by 14 people, representing 50.0%, and as very necessary by 14 people, representing 50.0%. The criterion "Extracurricular sports activities" (Q4) was selected as necessary by 18 people, accounting for 64.3%, and as very necessary by 10 people, accounting for 35.7%. The criterion "The need for sports training among students" (Q5) was selected as normal by 4 people, accounting for 14.3%; as necessary by 13 people, accounting for 46.4%; and as very necessary by 11 people, accounting for 39.3%. The criterion "Students' interest in learning 5-a-side football" (Q6) was chosen by 12 people at the "necessary" level, accounting for 42.9%, and by 16 people at the "very necessary" level, accounting for 57.1%. The criterion "Students' Physical Fitness Level" (Q7) received 12 votes for "Necessary," representing 42.9%, while 16 votes were for "Very Necessary," representing 57.1%. The criterion "Academic results" (Q8) was selected by 7 people at the "normal" level, accounting for 25.0%; at the "necessary" level, it was selected by 11 people, accounting for 39.3%; and at the "very necessary" level, it was selected by 10 people, accounting for 35.7%. Thus, among the 8 evaluation criteria, the percentage of those selected as necessary and very necessary ranged from 28.6% to 57.1%, with no opinions selected as unnecessary or very unnecessary, representing 0.0%. In addition, to consider the overall calculation results for each criterion, the study also conducted descriptive statistics on the selection criteria in Table 3.4 as follows:

Table 3.4: Descriptive statistical results of the selection of evaluation criteria

Item Statistics				
Encryption	Criteria	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Q1	Teaching staff requirements	4.42	.741	28
Q2	Facilities and equipment necessary for teaching and learning	4.39	.628	28
Q3	Content and curriculum	4.50	.509	28
Q4	Extracurricular sports activities	4.35	.487	28
Q5	The need for sports training among students	4.25	.700	28
Q6	Students' interest in learning 5-a-side football	4.57	.503	28
Q7	Students' Physical Fitness Level	4.57	.503	28
Q8	Academic results	4.10	.785	28

The results shown in Table 3.4 indicate that the evaluation criteria have mean values ranging from 4.25 to 4.57, standard deviations from 0.487 to 0.700. The question posed had five response levels, and the interviewed subjects answered from levels 3 to 5. This suggests that the interviewed subjects chose levels ranging from necessary to very necessary. To ensure the reliability of the interview responses, the study also conducted a Cronbach's Alpha reliability test for the criteria. The results are presented in Table 3.5 as follows:

Table 3.5: Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.908	.907	8

The results in Table 3.5 show that the 8 criteria have an overall Cronbach's Alpha reliability of 0.908. This confirms the reliability of the criteria when used to assess the current state of physical education at UFM.

As researchers and lecturers at the Faculty of National Defense and Physical Education of UFM, we wholeheartedly agree with the above contributions. Based on these criteria, it is possible to measure the effectiveness according to the general characteristics of the sports being taught at UFM in general, and 5-a-side football in particular.

Through research steps, eight criteria were identified to evaluate the effectiveness of learning 5-a-side football for students at the University of Finance - Marketing, Vietnam, including: teaching staff, facilities for teaching and learning, curriculum content, extracurricular sports activities, students' need for sports training, students' interest in learning 5-a-side football, students' physical fitness level, and learning outcomes.

DISCUSSION

The research results identified eight criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of 5-a-side football learning at UFM. This system of criteria was developed based on previous studies by Hoang Ha (2016), Nguyen Hung Anh (2013), Tran Duy Nam (2016), Nusri et al. (2025), Nugroho and Tomoliyus (2019) ... and is also suitable for the characteristics of 5-a-side football teaching at UFM.

Compared to previous studies that primarily focused on ensuring conditions, physical fitness, and academic performance, this study has the advantage of developing a more comprehensive system of criteria. It not only evaluates input and output factors but also incorporates psychological and motivational elements such as training needs and learning enthusiasm. In particular, the criteria "learning enthusiasm" and "physical fitness level" have the highest average values (Mean = 4.57), demonstrating their important role in the learning effectiveness of 5-a-side football.

Furthermore, the criterion "extracurricular sports activities," although not widely used in previous studies, received a high consensus rate from experts (93.33%), indicating that it is an important supporting factor in improving academic performance and developing sports activities among students.

In particular, the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient reached 0.908, confirming the high reliability of the 8-criterion system. This is a prominent advantage of the study, as it not only inherits the theoretical basis from previous works but also tests practical applications and statistical reliability, ensuring scientific validity and applicability in evaluating the effectiveness of 5-a-side football learning at UFM.

4. CONCLUSION

The study identified eight criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of learning 5-a-side football for students at the University of Finance - Marketing, Vietnam, including: teaching staff, facilities for teaching and learning, curriculum content, extracurricular sports activities, students' need for sports training, students' interest in learning 5-a-side football, students' physical fitness level, and academic results.

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